

A Study on Consumers’ Perception towards Organic Products with Special Reference to Thoothukudi District

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Abstract

The organic food industry is growing at fast rate on a world wide basis and is now has been the matter of much media attention over the past decade. Over the past several years, the organic food industry in India has been experiencing an annual growth between 20-22 percent . India has the potential to be largest organic food producer. In India, there are over 15000 certified organic farms and the number is growing fast over the years. According to the Indian Competence Centre for organic agriculture, the global market for organically produced food is \$26 billion and is estimated to increase to \$102 billion by 2020 . Food is the means to survival conversely, people are alert of the fact that the food people eat is adulterated and contaminated. The reason behind this being the use of chemicals to ripen the fruits and retain the freshness of vegetables. This can prove deadly to our health in the long run, rather than benefiting us. This increasing awareness has caused shifts in consumers’ tastes and preferences which have led to the domestic as well as global rise in demand for organic products.

Organic food awareness in the society and consumers has been increasing day by day but purchasing behaviour of organic food products is difficult because organic food products are available in the market together with conventional ones and the buying decision depends on many factors such as health and environmental attitudes and socio- demographic characteristics that can vary sharply across individuals. This study attempted to gain knowledge about consumption and how socio- economic variables relate to consumer buying behaviour concerning the purchase of organic foods on the title “ A Study on consumers’ perception towards organic products with special reference to Thoothukudi District” is chosen.

Introduction

The organic food industry is growing at fast rate on a world wide basis and is now has been the matter of much media attention over the past decade. Over the past several years, the organic food industry in India has been experiencing an annual growth between 20-22 percent. India has the potential to be largest organic food producer. In India, there are over 15000 certified organic farms and the number is growing fast over the years.

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estimated to increase to \$102 billion by 2020 Food is the means to survival conversely, people are alert of the fact that the food people eat is adulterated and contaminated. The reason behind this being the use of chemicals to ripen the fruits and retain the freshness of vegetables. This can prove deadly to our health in the long run, rather than benefiting us. This increasing awareness has caused shifts in consumers' tastes and preferences which have led to the domestic as well as global rise in demand for organic products.

Statement of the Problem

Organic food awareness in the society and consumers has been increasing day by day but purchasing behaviour of organic food products is difficult because organic food products are available in the market together with conventional ones and the buying decision depends on many factors such as health and environmental attitudes and socio- demographic characteristics that can vary sharply across individuals. This study attempted to gain knowledge about consumption and how socio- economic variables relate to consumer buying behaviour concerning the purchase of organic foods on the title "A Study on consumers' perception towards organic products with special reference to Thoothukudi District" is chosen.

Objectives of the Study

1. To know the reasons for purchase of organic products.
2. To know the benefits derived after using organic products.
3. To find out the level of attitude of consumers towards the purchase of organic products.
4. To offer suggestions based on the findings of the study.

Methodology

This study is based both on primary data and secondary data. The primary data was collected from the respondents directly with the help of questionnaire. The secondary data was collected from books, journals and websites. In Thoothukudi District, there are 11 organic stores available. From each store, 11 consumers are selected by convenient sampling method. The total is 121 is rounded off to 120. Hence 120 is the sample size. The questionnaire was distributed to the consumers of organic products directly and information was collected for analysis purpose. Garrett ranking technique was used to rank the benefits received after using organic products. The level of attitude towards purchasing of organic products on various dimensions was analysed with the help of 't' test.

Hypothesis to be Tested

In order to study the consumers' perception towards organic products, the following hypothesis was formulated.

The level of attitude of the sample respondents do not differ significantly towards the purchase of organic products on various dimensions like Health Safety, Environmental friendly and Animal Welfare, Quality, Purchase intention of organic products and Actual purchase behaviour of organic products.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

The collected data are analysed in three parts.

Reasons for Purchasing Organic Products

There are different reasons to buy organic products. In order to find the first and foremost reason to buy organic products, mean score is calculated. The results are presented in Table 1

Table 1

S. No	Reason	Rank Mark (x)	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	XIII	XIV	Total	Score $\frac{\sum FX}{\sum F}$	Rank
			14	13	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1			
1	More Variety	F	2	2	4	2	2	2	2	2	6	4	10	18	20	44	120	3.58	XII
		F(x)	28	26	48	22	20	18	16	14	36	20	40	54	40	44	424		
2	Good quality	F	14	16	4	8	6	6	8	8	4	14	12	10	4	6	120	8	VIII
		F(x)	196	208	48	88	60	54	64	56	24	70	48	30	8	6	960		
3	Tasty	F	8	12	2	10	10	10	6	8	12	8	14	2	14	4	120	7.51	X
		F(x)	112	136	24	110	100	90	48	56	72	40	56	6	28	4	902		
4	More Attractive	F	12	14	20	6	6	4	10	6	6	10	14	0	8	4	120	8.63	IV
		F(x)	168	182	240	66	60	36	80	42	36	50	56	0	16	4	1036		
5	Nutritional value	F	10	8	10	10	12	18	14	8	8	12	0	4	4	2	120	8.78	II
		F(x)	140	104	120	110	120	162	112	56	48	60	0	12	8	2	1054		
6	No Chemicals	F	0	0	2	4	2	0	8	2	0	4	8	34	32	24	120	3.4	XIV
		F(x)	0	0	24	44	20	0	64	14	0	20	32	102	64	24	408		
7	Superior to conventional food	F	10	8	20	10	12	12	14	10	8	4	2	4	0	6	120	9.25	I
		F(x)	140	104	240	110	120	108	121	70	48	20	8	12	0	6	1107		
8	Social status	F	4	8	8	14	12	10	4	14	16	14	6	4	2	4	120	7.5	XI
		F(x)	56	104	96	154	60	90	32	98	96	70	24	12	4	4	900		
9	Healthy	F	10	12	12	20	8	4	10	6	8	12	4	4	6	4	120	8.75	III
		F(x)	140	156	144	220	80	36	80	42	48	60	16	12	12	4	1050		
10	Environment friendly	F	12	12	10	6	8	6	10	18	16	10	6	2	2	2	120	8.6	VI
		F(x)	168	156	120	66	80	54	80	126	96	50	24	6	4	2	1032		
11	Temporary Fashion	F	12	8	8	10	18	12	8	12	6	8	10	4	4	0	120	8.41	VII
		F(x)	168	104	96	110	180	108	64	84	36	40	40	12	8	0	1010		
12	Ethical Reasons	F	16	4	6	8	12	16	10	8	16	6	14	2	0	2	120	8.55	V
		F(x)	224	32	72	88	126	144	80	56	96	30	56	6	0	2	1026		
13	No Adverse effects	F	6	6	8	6	10	14	18	8	14	12	6	4	4	4	120	7.6	IX
		F(x)	84	78	96	66	100	126	144	56	84	30	24	12	8	4	912		
14	Good value for money	F	2	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	0	4	10	40	30	22	120	3.43	XIII
		F(x)	28	26	24	22	0	18	16	14	0	20	40	120	60	22	410		

From Table 1 it is cleared that most of the respondents purchase organic products for the reason "Superior to conventional Food" (9.25) which is ranked in the first position

B. Benefits Received after using Organic Products

There are different benefits derived by the sample respondents after using organic products. In order to find out the main benefit derived by the sample respondents, Garrett Ranking technique is used. It is presented in Table -2

Table 2

S.No	Benefits	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	Mean Score	Rank
1	Organic farming better standards of animal welfare	6	2	2	8	10	26	66	90.08	VIII
2	Producing food organically allows wildlife to flourish	20	20	8	12	18	16	26	229.78	IV
3	Organic produce is healthier	46	18	18	12	14	10	2	353.45	I
4	Producing food organically helps reduce carbon foot print	14	16	12	14	14	24	40	205.2	VI
5	Organic produce tends to better quality	8	18	24	20	26	22	2	228.2	V
6	Organic food tastes better	8	18	30	34	18	8	4	249.4	III
7	Organic products represents good value for money	12	30	28	22	20	6	2	283.3	II

Hence it was cleared that ‘Organic produce is healthier’ was considered as the main benefit of using organic products by the sample respondents since it got the maximum score of 353.45

C. Attitude of Buyers towards the Purchase of Organic Products – Dimension Wise Analysis

Table 3 shows the result of mean, standard deviation, co-efficient of variation and 't' value with regard to the analysis of attitude of buyers towards the purchase of organic products on the basis of various dimensions.

Table 3**Attitude of buyers towards the Purchase of Organic Products- Dimension wise Analysis**

S.No.	Attitude towards organic products	Mean	S.D	C.V	T-value	Rank
1.	Health	3.02	1.48	49.00	0.072	V
2.	Safety	3.10	1.37	44.19	0.39	II
3.	Environmental friendly and animal welfare	3.02	1.52	50.23	0.070	VI
4.	Quality	3.07	1.47	47	0.26	IV
5.	Purchase intention of organic products	3.39	1.50	44.30	0.139	III
6.	Actual purchase behaviour of organic products	3.93	1.58	40.20	1.42	I

Significant at 0.05 level Table value at 0.05 level perception for degree of freedom $(n-1) = (6-1) = 5$.

From Table 3, it was observed that, with regard to the attitudes towards purchase of organic products, the mean scores of all the factors were above the neutral point(3). Hence the attitude of buyers towards the purchase of organic products were satisfied in all dimensions.

“Actual Purchase behaviour of organic products’ score the least value of co-efficient of variation (40.20) and it is selected as the first and foremost influencing dimension with regard to their attitudes towards purchase of organic products. It was proved by 't' test at 5% level of significance

Suggestions

- The manufacturer of organic products should improve the product features now and then to increase the consumption of organic products.
- The familiarity of the organic products among customers depends on the promotional efforts of the marketers. The availability organic food products need wider advertisement. So the manufacturers or dealers should take effective steps about the offers or discounts to inform the consumers.
- The Super markets or Department stores must allocate separate place to keep organic products and also it must be displayed attractively to induce the consumers to buy organic products.
- The dealer or the concerned authority must arrange programmes to educate the consumers to know the benefits of organic products and build them more environmentally conscious 'Green Consumer'.
- The agriculture marketing and co-operative department should verify to help farmers through certification by the organic certification department, which help them to get a good price.

Conclusion

An attempt has been made in this study to evaluate what influences the consumers to purchase organic food products. The consumers' perception about organic products are fair and good. Awareness about organic products, availability of organic products, and the benefits of using organic products are necessary in the present day marketing era. Consumers should make a move to green marketing by buying organic products. It makes them hail and healthy.